

DESIGN OF THE SMART COMPONENTS BASED ON SHAPE MEMORY EFFECT

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SUMMARY: A simple one-dimensional model and 2-D multi-fiber finite element (FE) model are employed to study not only the thermally induced stresses and strains but also the thermal expansion of polymer matrix composite (PMC) with continuous TiNi fiber. It is found that both the back stress in the PMC induced by stiffness of TiNi fibers and the compressive stress in the matrix are the major source of the strengthening mechanisms and low thermal expansion of composite. Based on the concept of so-called shape memory composite (SMC), the critical modulus ratio (CMR) between TiNi fiber and matrix is predicted to design and manufacture the smart components that have no or minimum thermal deformation under the repeated heating and cooling cycles. It is also found that SMC with modulus ratio that is larger than CMR shows no shape memory effect as the number of heating/cooling cycle increases. Experimentally, thermal deformation and tensile strength of SMC are measured to compare with the theoretical and numerical prediction. SMC shows the constant thermal strain after many thermal cycles.

KEYWORDS: shape memory composite, intelligent or smart material, shape memory alloy, thermal expansion coefficient, critical modulus ratio, thermal cycle

INTRODUCTION

Noise due to thermal non-uniformity within the various electronic packages can be a major source of consumer's dissatisfaction. If the thermal stress in several components coming from thermal non-uniformity can not be removed by the simple design changes due to the various reasons such as structural integrity, etc. The thermal stress as a source of noise should be offset by other means such as shape memory effect using shape memory alloys.

The phenomenon known as shape memory effect (SME) is the occurrence of a martensitic phase transformation and its subsequent reversal upon heating or cooling to a critical temperature. Basically, a shape memory alloy (SMA) is deformed in the martensitic condition and the shape memory recovery occurs during heating when the specimen undergoes a reverse transformation of the martensite to its parent phase [1,2,3]. Material functional properties of SMA change depending on the temperature. As a unique mechanical property, SMA shows a higher stiffness (2-3 times), higher yield stress and larger recovery stress at the higher temperature region due to inversely thermoelastic phase transformation in opposition to becoming weak in the general metals. Also, SMA has a high damping and high wear resistance. Another phenomenon due to the transformation between austenite and martensite is superelasticity. In this case, the strain recovers just by unloading at the temperature above a

reverse transformation temperature (A_f). This is caused by the strain-induced martensitic transformation upon loading and the reverse transformation upon unloading.

Using this SMA, an active composite can be made by a pre-stressed martensitic SMA fiber with a non-SMA matrix material. When the composite is heated, the fiber contracts due to transformation, thereby producing the large recovery energy to heal the damage in the composite structures and to improve various mechanical properties. Upon cooling, the austenite transforms into martensite, and the internal stresses within the matrix partially return the composite structure to its original shape. Recently, this active composites or SMC as known as intelligent material are widely studied[6-9].

In the present work, the simple theoretical and 2-D elastic-plastic FE analyses have been used to examine the effects of modulus ratio(MR) between fiber and matrix, fiber volume fraction, fiber shape, the stress/strain system in the composite. And their effects on the thermo-mechanical behavior of composite are studied in the aspect of shape memory composite(SMC) that showed the permanent effects for the repeated heating/cooling cycles with no or minimum thermal deformation.

ANALYTICAL MODELLING

The effective thermomechanical responses of SMA fiber and SMC will be evaluated first in theoretical section. Based on the micromechanics scheme by the Mori-Tanaka method[7-9], the thermomechanical constitutive equations for the TiNi SMA fiber are developed. Also, a simple 1-D model is developed to study the thermal expansion coefficient(CTE) of this active composite.

Theoretical Approach

The thermomechanical behavior[10] of a NiTi SMA fiber is expressed for uniaxial tension as

$$\sigma = E\varepsilon + \Phi T + \Omega \xi \tag{1}$$

$$\text{and } \xi = f(\sigma, T) \tag{2}$$

where E is SMA material elastic modulus, Φ is the thermal elastic modulus, Ω is the transformation constant and ξ is the volume fraction of martensite.

From Eqn(2), volume fraction of martensite is function of temperature and stress. And during martensite transformation(cooling), ξ is

$$0 = f(0, M_s), \quad 1 = f(0, M_f) \tag{3}$$

and during austenite transformation

$$1 = f(0, A_s), \quad 0 = f(0, A_f) \tag{4}$$

where M and A refer to martensite and austenite also the subscripts s and f refer to start point and finish point of transformation.

In above equation, the elastic modulus and the average elastic modulus as a function of temperature are

$$E = E_A + \xi (E_M + E_A) \quad \text{and} \quad E_{avg} = (E_M + E_A) / 2 \quad (5)$$

where the subscripts M and A refer to martensite and austenite, respectively.

Based on the 1-D model for SMA material[7,10], the equations for SMA fiber martensite transformation can be given as

$$\xi = 1 - \exp [b_M c_M (M_s - T) + b_M \sigma] \quad M_s \leq T \leq M_f \quad (6)$$

and for a reverse transformation can be

$$\xi = \exp [b_A c_A (A_s - T) + b_A \sigma] \quad A_s \leq T \leq A_f \quad (7)$$

where the material parameters c_M , b_M , c_A and b_A are given in Ref.[10].

Shape memory effect is occurred during a reverse transformation and the shape memory thermal strain is

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon_M^f + (\Omega / D) (\xi_M^f - \xi) \quad (8)$$

where the transformation constant, Ω , is variable depending on pre-strain. And if the transformation is complete when $\xi = 0.99$. And the volume fraction of martensite from the beginning point of a reverse transformation can be

$$\xi = \xi_M^f \exp [b_A c_A (A_s - T) + b_A \sigma] \quad A_s \leq T \leq A_f \quad (9)$$

From Eqn. (8)

$$Pre - strain (PS) = \frac{\Omega}{D} = \frac{\varepsilon - \varepsilon_M^f}{\xi_M^f - \xi} \quad (10)$$

Combining Eqns. (5) and (10)

$$\Omega = PS [E_A + \xi (E_M - E_A)] \quad (11)$$

If a reverse transformation is completed, the SMA fiber will be recovered up to pre-strain since $\xi_M^f = \xi$. Therefore, it is possible to predict the thermal constitutive behavior of pre-strain SMA fiber as a function of temperature. As a composite with SME, Fig. 1 shows the basic model for continuous SMA fiber reinforced composite. Step(a) is a composite model with martensite TiNi fiber and epoxy matrix under pre-strain. Both fiber and matrix have no stresses but have a residual tensile pre-strain(ε_p). As the temperature increases above A_f , Step(b) shows a condition that the matrix tends to have a tensile thermal strain due to thermal

expansion while the SMA fiber tends to shrink up to the pre-strain due to SME. Therefore, as shown in Step(c), there will be a tensile stress in the TiNi fiber and a compressive stress in the matrix due to the thermo-mechanical coupling. As a composite material, amount and direction of thermal strain of this intelligent material will be determined not only by the degree of SME, volume fraction and distribution of SMA fiber but also by the properties of matrix. So, it is possible to predict and control the thermo-mechanical properties of this TiNi/matrix composite using theoretical and numerical analyses.

At Step(b), if it is assumed that both matrix and fiber deform under iso-strain condition and their interface also deforms as a continuous media with increasing the temperature uniformly, the equilibrium equation of this composite material will be

$$\sigma_m v_m + \sigma_f v_f = 0 \quad (12)$$

where the subscripts m and f represent matrix and fiber, respectively. V is a volume fraction of material. Therefore, at Step(b), the matrix will have a compressive stress due to the thermo-mechanical bonding and the compressive strain will be

$$\alpha_m \Delta T + \epsilon_c = \frac{\sigma_m}{E_m} \quad (13)$$

where α_m is the thermal expansion coefficient of matrix and ϵ_c is the thermal strain of composite. Also, the fiber will have a tensile stress and the tensile strain will be

$$\alpha_f \Delta T + \epsilon_c = \frac{\sigma_f}{E_f} \quad (14)$$

where α_f is the shape memory thermal expansion coefficient(SMTEC) of pre-strain fiber with increasing temperature above A_f .

Combining Eqn(13) and Eqn(14), the compressive stress in the matrix can be obtained as

$$\sigma_m = \frac{(\alpha_m - \alpha_f) \Delta T E_m E_f v_f}{E_f v_f + E_m v_m} \quad (15)$$

Also, the tensile stress in the fiber can be determined by

$$\sigma_f = \frac{(\alpha_m - \alpha_f) \Delta T E_m E_f v_m}{E_f v_f + E_m v_m} \quad (16)$$

From Eqn. (14), one can write

$$\frac{\epsilon_c}{\Delta T} = \frac{\alpha_f E_f v_f + \alpha_m E_m v_m}{E_c} = \alpha_c \quad (17)$$

where $E_c = E_f v_f + E_m v_m$ and α_c is the SMTEC of composite material. Therefore, it is possible to predict the SMTEC of composite as a function of V_f . However, there will be a nonlinear deformation in the elastoplastic matrix due to a large compressive stress coming from a

reverse transformation of TiNi fiber. It is necessary to expand the 1-D elastic theory to elastic-plastic model. Several different approaches have been employed. It will be published later.

Fig. 1 Analysis model of continuous TiNi fiber reinforced composites.

Fig. 2 Thermal expansion (a) and elastic modulus (b) of TiNi fiber as a function of temperature and pre-strain.

Numerical Analysis

The model used for FE analysis is the same as the theoretical approach with continuous fiber. The used temperatures are $M_f=5^\circ\text{C}$, and $M_s=23^\circ\text{C}$ as the finish and starting temperatures for martensite transformation. $A_s=29^\circ\text{C}$ and $A_f=51^\circ\text{C}$ are the starting and finishing temperatures for reverse transformation temperature as independent properties, respectively. Also elastic modulus is $E_M=13\text{Gpa}$ and $E_A=30\text{Gpa}$, Poisson's ratio is 0.33 for matrix and fiber. And tangent modulus of TiNi is 1% of elastic modulus. The elastic modulus and the thermal expansion coefficient are changing according to Eqns.(5) and (8), respectively and are shown in Fig. 2. This data is used for all numerical computation. For the matrix, elastic modulus is $D_{ave.}/MR$, and thermal expansion coefficient is $55\text{E-}6(/^\circ\text{C})$ as a temperature independent properties. All these properties data are selected from the published data[10]. FE analysis is performed by changing the temperature from 0°C to 100°C , the fiber volume fraction of 0.5% and 1%. The used element type is 4-node isoparametric element. The numbers of element are chosen for optimum condition and are same for all analyzing model types. Also, the stress-strain curves, determined by the bilinear kinematics hardening rule, materials' elastic modulus and yield stress are given as input data. To obtain stress-strain behavior numerically, a far field tensile strain is loaded from 0% and 5% stepwise. Each step has 20 small substeps and iteration of substeps is carried out until satisfying the permit error of $10\text{E-}4$. To solve the non-linearity, Newton-Raphson's method has been employed. All computations are performed by the general purpose FE program, ANSYS 5.0[11]. And their boundary conditions are $u=0$ at $x=0$ and $v=0$ at $y=0$ where u and v is amount of displacement in the x and y directions, respectively. Both stresses and strains in the fiber and matrix are obtained based on the average values from the total volume of model. Then, the average stresses and strains of composite are determined as

$$[\varepsilon]_c = [\varepsilon]_m v_m + [\varepsilon]_f v_f \quad \text{and} \quad [\sigma]_c = [\sigma]_m v_m + [\sigma]_f v_f \quad (18)$$

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

TiNi fiber(Ti-50.2% Ni) of 0.1, 0.3 and 0.5 mm diameter are obtained from Nilaco Inc., Japan. The specimens are made with 0.5 and 1 volume percentage of SMA fiber. The epoxy resins used in this study are Type GT Series(Che-il Ciba-Geigy). Before making the composite specimens, the single fiber pull-out test is performed to obtain the best interfacial properties in the SMA fiber/epoxy system. It is found that the specimens with SMA etched the surface with 25% nitric acid for 25 sec. show the best interfacial strength among many surface treatments such as oxidation and mechanical abrasion techniques. The fibers are then vacuum heat treated for 1 hour at 50°C to remove all remaining solution inside the surface grooves and holes.

Specimen Fabrication

In this study, the continuous TiNi fiber reinforced composites as a candidate for this purpose are made. The fiber holder is used to apply 2 & 4 % pre-strain and hold for curing in a mold. Then, the fibers can be embedded in epoxy to depths in the range of 0.5 with the fiber axis perpendicular to the surface. The epoxy is allowed to harden according to manufacture's

Fig. 3 Theoretical prediction of thermal strain in TiNi/epoxy composite($v_f=10\%$) with 2% pre-strain (a) and 4% pre-strain (b).

Based on the theoretical analysis, Figs. 4 show the numerical prediction with elastoplastic analysis when $V_f=0.5\%$ and the applied pre-strain is 4%. Fig. 4(a) shows the thermal strain of fiber after transformation. As the MR increases, the TiNi fiber shows the compressive strain. And as the MR decrease, the TiNi fiber shows the tensile strain due to thermal expansion of matrix. Fig. 4(b) shows the thermal strain of matrix. Before the transformation, matrix shows the thermal expansion with the simple reinforcing effects by the fiber. After the transformation, composite shows the thermal expansion due to matrix as temperature increase for low MR. As the MR increases, composite will have a thermal shrinkage due to SME of the fiber. Based on this figure, there will be no thermal deformation of matrix around 60 when MR is 50 to 1.

Fig. 4 Numerical prediction of thermal strain in fiber(a) and matrix(b) as a function of temperature and modulus ratio.

Fig. 5 Numerical prediction of thermal strain in TiNi/matrix composite($v_f=1.0\%$) with (a)2% pre-strain and (b) 4% pre-strain.

Compared to Fig. 3, Figs. 5 show the numerical prediction of thermal strain of SMC with $V_f = 1.0\%$ when the given pre-strain is 2% and 4% respectively. Compared to Figs. 3, the thermal strains of SMC with 2% and 4% pre-strain after transformation are similar to matrix when MR is low. As the MR increases, the effects of pre-strain also increase. In the case of SMA fiber with 2% pre-strain, the compressive strain(ϵ_c) is occurred when MR is 50:1. With 4% pre-strain, SMC has ϵ_c even when MR is 25:1. This is quite different MR ranges compared with the theoretical prediction(Figs. 3). And this data shows the need to develop the theoretical model that considers the elastoplastic behavior.

Figs. 6 show the minimum thermal strain of different conditions as a function of MR after transformation for TiNi fiber and SMC, respectively. As shown in both figures, the thermal strain decreases linearly as the temperature increases. From Fig. 6(a), it is possible to predict the relationship between V_f and pre-strain. For low MR, the thermal behavior of TiNi fiber depends on the matrix after transformation while TiNi fiber exhibits SME as the MR increases. Therefore, the critical modulus ratio(CMR) can be determined from this type of figures. Table 1 shows the CMR of TiNi/epoxy composite predicted by FEM.

Table 1. FEM Prediction of Critical Modulus Ratio

Modulus Ratio(M_f/M_m)	$v_f=0.5\%$ Prestrain 2%	$v_f=0.5\%$ Prestrain 4%	$v_f=1\%$ Prestrain 2%	$v_f=1\%$ Prestrain 4%
TiNi Region	29.5	22.5	14.5	11.3
Composite	54.2	51.2	26.8	24.2

Fig. 6 Minimum thermal strain of TiNi fiber(a) and composite(b) as a function of modulus ratio and volume fraction.

Fig. 7(a) shows the stress-strain curves of TiNi fiber at 20, 45 and 65 °C. As known for SMA, both elastic modulus and yielding stress increase with the temperature. Fig. 7(b) shows the loading and unloading responses of TiNi fiber with 4% and 6% pre-strain. Regardless of the pre-strain amount, the SME of fiber is good.

Fig. 8 shows the thermal strain of TiNi fiber/epoxy with 4% pre-strain and 0.5 mm fiber as a function of temperature and thermal cycles. During few thermal cycles in the beginning, thermal expansion is much low due to SME of fiber. As the number of thermal cycle increases, thermal expansion becomes large. This trend is observed with even 0.1 mm TiNi fiber. Fig. 9 shows the thermal strain at 65 °C as a function of thermal cycles. As the number of thermal cycle increases, thermal expansion of SMC becomes constant. This represents the recovery of the major part of SME within few heating/cooling cycles regardless of fiber volume fraction in the case of large diameter of SMA fiber. However, the composite with the smaller fiber diameter shows the longer SME. Thermal strain measured with strain gage in the middle of specimen over the matrix is lower than thermal strain with gage above the fiber. For this type of specimen with fiber diameter 0.5 cm, two SMA fibers are embedded in the middle section. Gage over the matrix in the middle of specimen gets affect from both SMA fibers while gage over the fiber gets influence by one fiber only. As shown in figure, the total thermal strain of SMC is much less than that of the matrix alone.

Fig. 7a Tensile stress-strain curves of TiNi as a function of temperature.
 Fig. 7b Tensile loading/unloading response for TiNi.

Fig. 8 Thermal strain of TiNi/epoxy for heating and cooling cycle.

Fig. 9 Thermal strain of TiNi/epoxy for heating/cooling with cycle number at 65°C.

CONCLUSION

A new design concept of SMC for no or minimum thermal deformation under repeated heating and cooling cycles is proposed. The 1-D theoretical model for continuous TiNi fiber reinforced composite has been developed to study the thermal behavior as a function of modulus ratio(MR). Based on theoretical and numerical analyses, the critical modulus ratio (CMR) for several types of SMC is suggested for design and manufacturing of smart components. After making composite with TiNi fiber and epoxy, the thermal behavior is measured and compared. Both simple reinforcing effects and SME of TiNi fiber are observed. It is also found that SMC with MR that is larger than CMR shows no SME as the number of heating/cooling cycle increases. Also, SMC shows the constant thermal strain after many thermal cycles.

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